

**AN INVESTIGATION INTO EFFECTS OF MARIJUANA SMOKING AMONGST
ADOLESCENTS: A CASE STUDY OF CHIBOLYA COMPOUND.**

Preston Mwiinga

Table of Contents

CHAPTER ONE	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.0 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Background of the study	1
1.2 Statement of the problem	3
1.3 General Study objectives	4
1.4 Specific objectives	4
1.5 Research questions.....	4
1.6 Significance of the study.....	5
1.7 Limitations of the study	5
1.8 Scope of the study.....	5
1.9 Theoretical framework.....	6
1.10 Conceptual framework.....	7
1.11 Definition of terms	8
CHAPTER TWO	12
LITERATURE REVIEW	12
2.0 Introduction.....	12
2.1 Concepts of drugs and drug abuse	12
2.2 Global studies on the effects of marijuana smoking on adolescents.....	13
2.3 Studies in Africa	15
2.4 Studies in Zambia.	17
2.5 Critique of previous studies and research gaps.....	19
CHAPTER THREE	21
METHODOLOGY	21
3.0 Introduction.....	21
3.1 Research design	21
3.2 Location of the study	21
3.3 Target population.....	21
3.4 Sampling techniques and sample size	22
3.5 Data collection instrument	22
3.6 Data collection procedures.....	22

3.7 Data presentation and analysis.....	22
3.8 Ethical consideration.....	23
REFERENCES	23

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

This chapter presents background to the study on the effects of marijuana smoking amongst adolescents. The chapter further presents the statement of the problem under investigation, the general objective of the study, research objectives and research questions. It also presents significance of the study, limitations, scope of the study, operational definitions, theoretical framework, and conceptual framework.

1.1 Background of the study

Marijuana is one of the world's most frequently used illicit drugs. Worldwide, it has been estimated that 147 million individuals (2.5 percent of world population) use marijuana (WHO, 2012). Marijuana is also often associated with popular 'youth culture' in that the starting age for marijuana is usually much lower than for other drugs (WHO, 2012). In the United States, for example, 16 percent of 8th graders and nearly 50 percent of 12th graders have used marijuana (Johnston et al., 2011). A number of U.S. states such as Washington and Colorado have recently approved the full legalization of marijuana use for adults aged 21 years or over, despite concerns including the potential for 'leakage' to younger age groups. It is a regular feature of many adolescents' lives, as approximately 20% of 15-year-olds worldwide had used marijuana in the past year (NHS Digital, 2018). Also, recent literature has shown that the phenomenon of substance abuse is prevalent across the whole world and appears to be on an upward trend community (WHO, 2022). The most commonly used substances are depressants, stimulants, hallucinogens, inhalants and opioids in nature. Marijuana use was historically characterized as a deviant behavior (Becker, 1953), but has become 'normalised' in the last 30 years (Hammersley et al., 2001), as indicated by high use rates (Hathaway et al., 2011).

World Health Organisation (2022), revealed that using substance continuously leads to addiction as the condition of being physically and psychologically dependent on the substance. This impacts negatively on biological, social, psychological or behavioural and economical dimensions be it on

society or institutions or upon an individual. The broader context of addictive substances has several important characteristics in common. They alter the function of the human brain and have an impact on behaviour; they are widely used throughout the world; and they burden society by increasing social and economic costs for productive enterprises and by drawing upon limited government services. The most widely used addictive substances, alcohol and marijuana, are harmful with extensive damage to the individual, family and the community (WHO, 2022).

Literature also shows that teenagers are more likely to use marijuana than adults (EMCDDA, 2015). Therefore, understanding adolescents' thoughts and attitudes about marijuana use is important. Marijuana produces desirable short-term effects, such as relaxation and euphoria (Green et al., 2003). However, heavy, long-term use is associated with a small increased risk of mental health problems and mild neurocognitive impairment (Curran et al., 2016).

Additionally, research has shown the effects of marijuana on the abusers. It is concluded that a range of 10- to 20-year-olds, roughly 12.4 % met criteria for substance use disorder like mbanje/marijuana, alcohol and other psychoactive drugs causing violent death for teenagers, including homicide, suicide, traffic accidents, detrimental consequences, violent behaviour, delinquency, psychiatric disorders, risky sexual behavior, possibly leading to unwanted pregnancy or sexually transmitted diseases, impulsivity and neurological impairment (Mafumbate, 2016). Pudney (2018) admits that substance abuse reflects teenagers being socially problematic to their families, causing bankruptcy by meeting medical costs or criminal fines. It had been purported that teenagers enjoy defying parents and other authority figures through school dropouts from learning institutions and at work. There is also high rate in impaired performance, lateness, intoxication, disciplinary problems and absenteeism (Pudney, 2018).

Similarly, literature shows that the abuse of drugs such as marijuana in Africa is not very different from other parts of the world (WHO, 2022). Traditionally, the use or abuse of drugs was confined to elderly people and mainly involved alcohol and marijuana. However, the rapid pace of economic and social development, and in some countries prevailing political instability, have seen the problem of drug and alcohol abuse escalating at a rapid rate. For instance, studies done in Lesotho and Kenya found out that 8.8% of 10 to 14 year old pupils and 42% of secondary school pupils were abusers of alcohol and marijuana respectively (Bourne, 2015). Lakhampal and Agnihotri (2017) say that Africa has become a major centre of consumption of drugs such as marijuana,

cocaine, heroin and other synthetic narcotics. In addition, Behaviourists identified various social negative results of substance abuse as intoxication may act in uncharacteristic and unsafe ways because both physical and mental functioning is impaired. In the cases of Uganda, Botswana, Zimbabwe and others in Sub Saharan Africa adolescents run a risk of multiple challenges, for instance, prostitution or rape and unintended pregnancy (Di Forti et al., 2019).

Zambia, like many African countries, is facing a problem of drug and alcohol abuse among the youth. Alcohol and marijuana are reported to be the most abused drugs followed by volatile solvents and hard drugs such as heroin and cocaine. Much of what is known about drug and alcohol abuse comes from the Drug Enforcement Commission (DEC, 2021) reports based on institutional arrests and counselling data, and treatment records from psychiatric clinics and hospitals. In Livingstone District, for example, eighty-seven pupils who abused drug and alcohol were recorded by National Education Campaign Division (NECD) of DEC during the period from 2007 to 2009 (DEC, 2009). This clearly shows that there is a lot of drug and alcohol abuse occurring in schools in Livingstone. The health, social and educational consequences of substance and alcohol abuse go beyond individual abusers to their families, communities and many other social and economic systems. In communities (compounds), drug and alcohol abuse is associated with problem behaviour such as truancy, rudeness, vandalism, lack of respect for authority and general delinquency (National Education Campaign Division, 2020).

It has been observed that the rising alcohol and marijuana abuse situation among youths in Zambia's Lusaka districts compounds has become a major social and health concern to the public (Masiye, Ndhlovu & Kasonde-Ng'andu, 2019). The government recognizes that alcohol and marijuana abuse among learners is a threat to social security and a hindrance to national development. Ekpenyong (2012) attributed high levels of indiscipline and riotous behaviors displayed by adolescents to drugs and alcohol use. The public is at risk given that people are the recipients of deviant of behavior resulting from juvenile delinquency and drug abuse. Thus, it is a source of concern that calls for immediate measures.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Marijuana is the most commonly used illicit drug among juveniles. The public outcry especially in the print and electronic media on drug abuse among juveniles has been persistent and calls for

efforts by every concerned citizen, the government and key stakeholders to play a key role in tackling this worrying concern, according to Drug Enforcement Commission reports((DEC, 2022). Alcohol and drug abuse among juveniles is becoming a problem in Zambia as a number of studies carried out in the country show that juveniles from compounds at one time or another experiment with drugs especially alcohol and marijuana (Masiye, Ndhlovu & Kasonde-Ng'andu, 2019). Research has shown that abuse of alcohol at earlier or young stage can affect the development of the brain and ruin the academic performance of a pupil (A Canadian Addiction Survey, 2018).

Despite the widespread use of marijuana among adolescents, qualitative research in this field is not adequate to account for all compounds in Lusaka district, Chibolya compound to be precise. The issue at hand is that cases are still being reported on drug abuse such as marijuana, especially in Lusaka compounds. To be more specific, the Drug Enforcement Commission (2022), reported that the youths of Chibolya Township have become prone to such negative vices. It appears to the researcher that these problems are because of lack of knowledge of the effects of marijuana among adolescents of Chibolya compound in Lusaka. Thus, in order to bridge the ignorance gap, this study endeavors to give a voice on the ongoing issues of drug abuse among adolescents by investigating the effects of marijuana on youths of Chibolya compounds.

1.3 General Study objectives

To establish effects of marijuana smoking amongst adolescents in Chibolya compound of Lusaka district.

1.4 Specific objectives

The study will be guided by the following objectives:

- i. To determine factors that influence adolescents to smoke marijuana.
- ii. The find out the extent to which marijuana is abused.
- iii. To identify the possible effects of smoking marijuana among adolescents.

1.5 Research questions

- i. What influences adolescents to smoke marijuana?

- ii. To what extent do adolescent smoke marijuana?
- iii. What are the possible effects of smoking marijuana on adolescents?

1.6 Significance of the study

It is hoped that the research findings and recommendations will contribute to the literature review and for reference's sake by other researchers within the perimeters of the study area. The findings are also expected to add to the improvement of various rehabilitation programmes run by the Juvenile Department in Zambia to deal with the problem of child offenders. More so, more knowledge will be revealed to these organisations facing these (child delinquency) problems and the public at large on how to curb them effectively and efficiently in order to maintain a conduct environment for the public interest. It is also hoped that the study findings are expected to sensitize and benefit the likes of parents/guardians, police officers, local government, social workers, criminology professors, Department of Criminal Justice Education, Children Psychologists and other interested stakeholder's through the issues revealed in this study. The study is also expected to benefit key government agencies such as Zambia Police (ZP), Drug Enforcement Commission (DEC), remand homes for juveniles, correctional facilities, rehabilitation centres, social workers and other interested stakeholders among others.

1.7 Limitations of the study

The research will be conducted within the researcher's budget. The researcher is hoping to have access to secondary data from DEC offices. Due to limited and poor management records in most government offices, the researcher may have challenges accessing earliest records on juvenile delinquency.

1.8 Scope of the study

The study will not focus on a wide range of all the compounds in Lusaka but Chibolya Township only. This implies that the findings will only reflect the situation of a single compound and not to be generalized to other compounds in Lusaka district.

1.9 Theoretical framework

The study will be guided by Bandura's Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977). The Social Learning Theory, also known as Social Cognitive Theory focuses on the learning that occurs within the social context. Firstly, it proposes that young people learn social behaviours through a process of observation and imitation of the role models and the outcome or consequences of their behaviour (Dembo, 1994). Role models and perceptions of the behaviour norms serve as social influences for engagement in that behaviour. Young people actively watch and imitate the behaviours of significant others in their life. These models include parents, teachers, peers and other adult people (Dembo, 1994). Secondly, the theory essentially purports triadic reciprocity between personal, environmental and behavioural factors. Personal factors include cognition, expectancies, beliefs and attitudes while environmental factors include contingencies of reinforcement. Behaviour factors include involvement in marijuana smoking. The behaviour depicted in young people is mostly as a result of the interaction of these three factors.

Additionally, the Modified Social Stress Model (MSSM) is another theory that attempts to reveal the understanding of drug use and the effects. The model was developed by Rodes and Jason (1988) and modified by World Health Organization/Programme on Substance Abuse (WHO/PSA) to include the effects of drugs or substances, the personal response of the individual to drugs and additional environmental, social and cultural variables. This theory is of the view that there are risk factors that encourage drug abuse. Factors that make people less likely to abuse drugs are called protective factors. According to this model, if many risk factors are present in a person's life, that person is more likely to begin, intensify and continue the use of drugs, which could lead to drug abuse. The model identifies risk factors as stress (which could be due to the school or home environment, and adolescent developmental changes) and normalization of substance use among others. In addition, there is also the experience derived from the use of drugs, which could be positive or negative. According to Rodes and Jason (1988), drugs which produce positive effects are likely to be abused. The model also shows that the more protective factors are present, the less likely the person is to become involved with drugs. Protective factors are identified as: attachments with people such as family members, peers and institutions such as religion and school.

The aforementioned theories have been used to explain factors that influence adolescents to abuse drugs and alcohol in society to which they belong. The theory has also helps the researcher to

understand that drug and alcohol abuse behaviour in adolescents is socially learnt from models such as peers, parents and the media, exposing them more to drug and alcohol abuse. In addition, such exposure will help adolescents to acquire knowledge about the consequences of abusing drugs and drug and alcohol attitudes and behaviours. It is easy to understand the drug problem better if both risk and protective factors are considered at the same time. Probability of drug abuse is determined by these factors. This theoretical model is useful for the study as a way of planning interventions to prevent or treat problems related to drug abuse. Besides the aforementioned risk and protective factors, there could be others which contribute to the present scenario in families, schools and communities. Therefore, the actual state of affairs needed exploration for factors unique to Lusaka District in Zambia where the study will be conducted. The above well outlined theories provide a basis for examining the effects of smoking marijuana on adolescents.

1.10 Conceptual framework

This conceptual framework forms a basis for the study with regard to independent and dependent variables. As clearly shown, substance abuse (Marijuana Smoking) constitutes what is termed to be the independent variables. On the other hand, crime increase, deviant behavior such as vandalism, attitude and behavior change and cognitive related challenges are the dependent variable of the study. The illustration implies that in the presence of drug abuse (Marijuana) by juveniles, the suggested dependent variables are likely to be the results.

Independent Variable

Substance abuse
(Marijuana Smoking)

Dependent Variables

- Crime increase
- Deviant behavior such as vandalism
- Attitude and behavior change
- Cognitive related challenges

1.11 Definition of terms

Abuse: a drug is considered abused by a person when s/he deliberately uses it for non-medical purposes, as well as the arbitrary use without medical prescription.

Abuse: Usage levels that have short-term acute personal or social consequences. **Drug:** Any substance which, when ingested by a living organism, alters one or more of its physiological

functions. They include, but not limited to, alcohol, tobacco, marijuana, inhalants, pain medications, and other hard drug use.

Addiction: is a chronic, progressive fatal use of drugs making withdrawal efforts dangerous.

Alcohol: a colourless volatile flammable liquid that is the intoxicating constituent of wine, beer, spirits, and other drinks.

Binge Drinking: consuming more than 5 alcoholic drinks in men and 4 alcoholic drinks in women per session.

Cosmopolitan: a city with a mixture of cultures.

Curb: to control or stop a situation or thing.

Delinquent act: This is behaviour that violates basic norms of society and when officially known it evokes a judgment by agents of criminal justice that such norms have violated.

Deviant behaviour: behaviour that does not conform to institutional rules, norms or regulations.

Discipline in school: functioning of a school according to what the school authorities consider as the rules of proper conduct and orderly action.

Discipline: refers to self-restraint in an individual for the welfare of all. It is control of one's emotions and action for the development of desirable attitudes according to acceptable standards.

Disruptive behaviour: this is any utterance or non-verbal action of a pupil which interferes with the intended learning objectives in a classroom at a specified time of instruction.

Drug abuse: This is the sporadic or persistent excessive use of any substance for any reason other than its acceptable medical use. Such use is normally unacceptable to the society and dangerous to the individual as well as society. 10

Drug dependence: is a desire to continue taking a drug, to induce pleasure or relieve tension and avoid discomfort.

Drug dependence: Repeated drug taking that usually results in a person needing drugs to function.

Drugs: are those man-made or naturally occurring substances used without medical supervision basically to change the way a person feels, thinks or behaves by altering the normal biological and psychological functioning of the body especially the nervous system.

Friendship groups: these are peer groups in which members are recruited as friends through existing friendship network.

Impact: ability to bring about change in knowledge, attitudes, beliefs and behaviour about drug and alcohol abuse among pupils.

Juvenile Crime: Various offenses committed by children or youths under the age of 18. Children's offenses typically include delinquent acts, which would be considered crimes if committed by adults, and status offenses, which are less serious misbehavior such as truancy and parental disobedience.

Juvenile delinquency: a legal term for behaviour of children and adolescents that in adults would be judged criminal under law. Juvenile delinquency is the violation of a law of Zambia committed by a person prior to his eighteenth birthday which would have been a crime if committed by an adult.

Juvenile: a person below the age of 16.

Legal/licit drug: A drug socially accepted and readily available. **Prevalence:** The magnitude of drug use among a particular population.

Minor: a person below the age of 18 according to cap 167 of the laws of Zambia.

Peer pressure: Tendency to conform to the values and expectations of the peer group.

Stakeholder: Any person, or group of people, who has an interest in and may be affected by the educational process taking place in schools in Shibuyunji district.

Substance Abuse: An excessive use of addictive substances especially when such consumption or misuse of a substance is not for therapeutic purposes but rather for the purpose of altering the normal functioning of the mind and body.

Substance use: A broad term that covers taking of all substances within which there are stages such as substance free (that is, non-use), experimental use, recreational use, and harmful use.

Substance: Any material or drug that produces changes in mood, thinking, feeling, and/or behaviour that can cause dependence. The three commonly used psychoactive drugs are alcohol, cigarette and marijuana.

Urban area: an area with improved infrastructure and high level of economic activity. The area is characterized by many people having access to electricity, health facilities, education facilities, housing, safe water and good sanitation.

Violence: refers to behaviour that is intended to hurt someone, for example bullying.

Youth: According to this study, youth are defined according to World Health Organisation and therefore youth refers to young people ranging to 10 and 24 years WHO (1993).

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter presents a review of relevant literature on the effects of smoking marijuana on adolescents. The chapter covers the concept of drugs and drug abuse, literature from the world perspective, African studies and Zambian investigations in particular. The chapter also includes the critique of the studies and possible research gaps to be investigated by this current study.

2.1 Concepts of drugs and drug abuse

A drug is defined as any natural or artificial substance, other than food, that by its chemical nature alters the structure or function of a living organism (Oakey & Charles, 2017). Gerrard et al. (1999) defined a drug as any chemical entity or mixture of entities other than those required for the maintenance of normal health (like food and medicine), the administration of which alters biological function and possibly structure. Ike (2009) introduced an element of danger to those who consume drugs in his definition. He described drugs as harmful and that they alter the organic functions and behaviour of those who take them. The definition given by the New Book of Knowledge (1992) puts emphasis on the pharmaceutical use of drugs that they are substances used to treat or prevent disease, to relieve pain, to help control mental or physical ailments, and even to help diagnose illness. From these definitions, it can be concluded that a drug is a chemical substance which can be taken by people for various purposes, medicinal or non-medicinal, and can either be beneficial or harmful to the people ingesting it.

In the context of this study, drugs will be taken to include marijuana. Marijuana comes from a plant (*Cannabis sativa*), it is natural but it has negative physiological and psychological effects. The Office of National Drug Control Policy (2007), reported that marijuana use is associated with a number of health conditions including frequent respiratory infections, impaired memory, irregular heart rates, panic attacks, anxiety, and learning impairments. These data coupled with social as well as legal consequences speak directly to the apparent harmful effects of marijuana

use. Due to the numerous views that society has adopted, perceptions are relative to individual life experiences.

When the subject of drug use comes up, it is often in relation to young people. This is because, for young people, use, even in moderation, constitutes abuse. Furthermore, the World Youth Report (2003) provided two reasons why the use of drugs by youths is topical. The first reason is that it is during the younger years that most substance use begins. At this stage, the young want to experiment on what they see elders do in their communities; they also want to show their peers that they are courageous and are not afraid of drugs. According to the report, if a person has not begun to use alcohol, tobacco or an illicit substance during this period, it is unlikely he or she ever will. The second reason is that young people in almost all countries tend to use substances to a greater extent and in riskier ways than do older people, and this behaviour can result in significant problems in the short- and long-terms. After years of continued use of drugs, young people develop a condition called drug dependence. This can be psychological, physiological, or both. Adolescence and young adulthood is, therefore, a critical period in the children's lives where they need positive role models and close guidance by adults. Connell et al. (2014) identified four patterns of drug use, namely non-users, experimenters, occasional users, and frequent users.

2.2 Global studies on the effects of marijuana smoking on adolescents

Various studies have been conducted on the effects of smoking marijuana across the global. Bourassa and Vaugoeis (2015) explored the impact of marijuana use on creativity (otherwise referred to as divergent thinking) as well as frequency of use and its impact on levels of creative thinking. One hundred male participants between the ages of 21 and 30 were randomly chosen based on their responses to a questionnaire on marijuana consumption. The participants were broken down into subgroups of 60 and identified (based upon questionnaire responses) as nonsmokers or smokers. The instrument used for this study was the Torrance Test of Creative Thinking. The researchers also used marijuana as well as a placebo of marijuana within the methodology. The results of the study revealed that marijuana use had no positive effects on creative or divergent thinking in non-users, while a significant reduction in creativity was noted in users (Bourassa and Vaugoeis, 2015). In a study on perceived risks of harm from marijuana use, Danseco, Kingery, and Coggshell (2019) sought to establish how risks of harm from marijuana

use are perceived based upon age and gender. The researchers also attempted to establish how existing nationally representative surveys and status of use influence perception. The sample consisted of a population of school-age students who had taken various surveys to assess their responses to questions to further gather conclusions regarding perceived risk of harm. The conclusion of the study the research findings indicated that there are consequences for the individual, family and society (Danseco, Kingery, and Cogshell, 2019).

Gonzalez et al, (2019) conducted a study on the effects of adolescent marijuana use on motivation and depression. The findings showed that heavy adolescent marijuana use predicts poorer educational outcomes, often presumed to reflect reduced academic motivation, as well as increased levels of depressive symptoms. However, evidence of a link between marijuana use and general motivation was lacking. Factors such as concurrent alcohol and marijuana use, trajectories of marijuana use during adolescence, and marijuana-related changes in underlying neurocircuitry may impact associations among marijuana use, motivation, and depression. A study by Karashiali et al., (2022) on cannabis, identity, and attitudes: a qualitative study in adolescents who do and do not use cannabis aimed at examining what London-based adolescents (aged 16-17 years) think about cannabis use, its relationships with identity, and its benefits and harms. Thematic analysis (TA) revealed four identities. Two identities emerged from both groups: 'The person who uses cannabis is chilled' and 'The person who uses cannabis is sometimes ostracised'. Two identities emerged from the group of adolescents who used cannabis: 'The person who uses cannabis is an expert in risky things' and 'The person who uses cannabis is not addicted'. Skunk was identified as potentially more harmful than hash, but more powerful and pleasurable. In addition, Karashiali et al., (2022) established that insight into how cannabis use shape personal and social identity amongst teenagers in London in the late 2010s. Those who use cannabis described the benefits of cannabis, including socialising and for relaxation, and emphasized they are not addicted. Stigmatizing and devaluing attitudes were held by some non-users about adolescents who use cannabis. Stereotypes seem to still exist, despite cannabis normalisation. Implications for research and policy are outlined.

Furthermore, González et. al., (2023) found in their study that personal problems, social problems or family problems can lead to cannabis use. There was a lack of knowledge and low risk perception about consumption of this drug. There are other factors that influence consumption, the

perception of advantages, such as the feeling of freedom and the influence of the peer group. The consumption of this substance in girls is changing, becoming more and more equal to that of boys. The family has an important role to play in preventing drug use. The authors additionally revealed that knowledge of these factors is of vital importance as a prior step to the development of efficient intervention measures adjusted to the needs identified and the characteristics of the population (González et. al., 2023). Also, Butler (2018) investigated on the association between cannabis use, depression, anxiety and flourishing in youth: a cross-sectional analysis from year 5 of the Compass Mental Health. The objective of the thesis was to examine if depression or anxiety were associated with youth cannabis use; and investigate whether flourishing moderated the associations. From the sample, 33% of participants had ever used cannabis, 51% and 38% reported elevated depressive and anxiety symptoms, respectively. Associations between depression, anxiety, and cannabis use were no longer significant when flourishing was added to the models. In addition, there was no evidence suggesting a moderating effect of flourishing as all interactions were not statistically significant. Instead, robust associations were found between flourishing and cannabis use. Indicators of mental wellbeing, such as flourishing, appear to be associated with a lower likelihood of cannabis use, even after controlling for depression and anxiety. According to Butler (2018), the result suggested prevention strategies for youth cannabis use should aim to foster mental wellbeing among all youth, rather than exclusively targeting those experiencing mental health problems.

2.3 Studies in Africa

In a study by Rehn et al, (2011), marijuana was reported to have caused an unnatural thirst or hunger, uncontrolled mood swings, talkativeness, perception impairments, disturbed judgment, disorders in mind, a wellbeing feeling, euphoria and anxiety alleviates All in all, the dangers of the use of marijuana consists excessive aggression as combined with alcohol, accidents due to distorted perception, physical damage in the form of bronchial irritation, risk of lung cancer, chromosome damage, and ultimately brain damage and this is normally the first stage of addiction before drug abusers shift to hard drugs (Rehn et al, 2011).

According to Agbonghalel and Okaka (2014), who investigated the effects of drug abuse on academic performance on technology education students in Nigerian public universities found that 82.79% of the population who participated in study agreed that hard drugs had some effects on

academic performance of technology education students in Nigerian public universities who were involved in drug abuse. According to Otieno (2012), who conducted a study on environmental and demographic factors influencing drug and substance abuse among secondary school students in Kisumu Town east in Kenya, indicated some statistical information from Kisumu District Hospital to have an increase in mental and behavioral disorders due multiple drug consumption and the use of other psychoactive substances (KDH Office, 2012). Similarly, Tuwei (2014) conducted a study on the influence of drug abuse on youths. Findings showed that marijuana smoking led to lack of studies' concentration, sleepless, lack of appetite, dodging classes, physical weakness, and rejection from the friends.

Muwanzi (2019), examined the causes, nature and effects of substance abuse among adolescents in Mabelreign community. It also identified mechanisms and strategies that could be adopted to reduce substance abuse. Methodologically adopted; survey research design, stratified random sampling size of 50 respondents and questionnaires and interview schedule were data gathering tools. The study revealed an increase of substance abuse among adolescents due to various reasons, but the researcher hypothesized 'the legal majority age' as the core cause which makes it difficult to manage adolescents. Further, a number of researchers and authors showed that drug addicts were affected in through various ways depending on the type of drugs one uses. For example, marijuana is said have caused relaxation, intensifies perception of stimuli, increases self-confidence, a sense of enhanced awareness and creativity, impairs motor coordination, reduces short term memory and distorts judgments (Osdol and Shane, 2017). Apart from its consequences, it should be understood that Marijuana may bring brain impairment, lack creative minds, and inability to think properly for students or youths taking marijuana (Santrock, 1984).

In relation to age, Faeh et al. (2017) reported that prevalence of ever used cannabis was more common among adolescents aged 15–17 years than in the 11–13 year and 14 years age groups. Khan and Arnott (2018) reported that use of cannabis increased with age among adolescents in Harare in Zimbabwe. Nkonge (2015), conducted a study on factors influencing drug and substance abuse among the youth in Kenya in Likii sub-location of Laikipia East Sub-County. The study adopted triangulation design that combines both qualitative and quantitative research techniques and measures (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). The data was collected using self-completion questionnaires administered to youths and community members and interview schedules for area

chief in addition to personal observations. This formed primary sources of data collection. The study population involved four villages, 120 youths and 120 community members drawn from 2189 households in Likii sub-location. The study findings indicated that alcohol was the most abused drug in the area, followed by marijuana. The study findings highlighted the factors influencing drug and substance abuse amongst the youths in Kenya, the community initiatives to curb the vice and the preparedness of National administration and other law enforcement agencies in arresting the situation.

Yawson et al., (2022) conducted a study on Marijuana use and suicidal behaviours among school-going adolescents in Africa: assessments of prevalence and risk factors from the Global School Based Student Health Survey. The study aimed at assessing factors associated with marijuana use and further quantify marijuana use as an associated factor of suicidal behaviours, including repeated attempted suicide, suicidal ideation and suicide planning, among high school students in Africa. The prevalence of marijuana use and repeated attempted suicide were 3.7% (95% CI: 3.1 to 4.3) and 6.6% (95% CI: 5.9 to 7.4), respectively. Yawson et al., (2022) concluded that marijuana use was significantly associated with suicidal behaviours (suicidal ideation, planning and repeated attempted suicide) among the students. To achieve Sustainable Development Goal (to strengthen prevention and treatment of substance abuse), school based psychosocial interventions should be streamlined to adequately assess and manage marijuana use. Targeting the most dominant risk factors in this population could translate into the reduction of suicidal behaviours in countries within Africa. Morojele et al, (2021) conducted a study on alcohol, tobacco, and other drug use among adolescents in sub-Saharan Africa. The survey revealed that alcohol, tobacco, and other drug (ATOD) use such as marijuana by adolescents are major contributors to death and disability in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Other findings included interpersonal violence, sexual risk behaviours, and negative academic outcomes.

2.4 Studies in Zambia.

Zemba (2022) conducted a study on the causes and effects of drug abuse on juveniles in Kitwe Township in Mindolo. Questionnaire and interviews were the instruments used to collect data and data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, (SPSS). The mean and the standard deviation were used to see the trends in the data. The results of the study reviewed that

alcohol and marijuana were frequently abused by adolescent and these resulted from factors such as peer pressure, low self-esteem, and availability of drugs. The abuse of these drugs has led deviant behavior and juvenile delinquency, the result of which there was crime increase in Mindolo area. Also, Kaluwe (2019), conducted a study on the effects of drug abuse on pupils' juvenile behavior. The researcher also used questionnaires and structured interviews as instruments for data collection. The study revealed that there were a number of factors that led to drug abuse and these were; peer pressure, genetic, curiosity and depression. Furthermore the study revealed that youths stay in communities where drugs were being sold and easily accessed.

Mulenga and Siziya`s (2021) study aimed at determining prevalence and associated factors of tobacco and marijuana smoking among secondary school going adolescents in Ndola Zambia. Method that was used for data collection was a self-administered questionnaire based cross-sectional survey of grades 8's and 10's in five regions of Ndola Zambia. Factors that were realized from the study included socio-economic and demographic variables, personal and family behaviour, peer behaviour and media exposure. In addition, Ndhlovu et a., (2019) sought to establish practices in drug and alcohol abuse prevention education in selected Lusaka township compounds in Zambia. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to collect, analyze and interpret both quantitative and qualitative data from 514 respondents. Findings of the study included other peers being bullied; alcohol and sexual intercourse were associated with history of having used marijuana.

Masenga (2017) researched on the impact of drug abuse among adolescents, The study aimed specifically to identify common types of drugs abused by the students, to explore causes of drug abuse among students in the study area, to assess rate of school attendance among children involved in drug abuse, finally to assess terminal and annual examination performance among students involved in drug abuse. Findings showed that majority of adolescents accepted that drug abuse is a negative sign towards their academic performance and one of the major reasons for drug abuse among the students was to be appreciated by friends and marijuana was said to be the most frequently abused drug followed by alcohol and cigarette. Addition to that, the rate of school or class attendance for students who involved in consumption of drugs was observed to be poor hence lead to low in academic performance (Masenga, 2017).

2.5 Critique of previous studies and research gaps

Literature has been reviewed from different studies across the world, and from the aforementioned studies, research gaps have been identified. In America, a study by Bourassa and Vaugoeis (2015) showed that marijuana had no positive effect on divergent thinking. However, in other context like Zambia, there are usually myths associated with smoking marijuana and good performance or thinking creatively and being energetic (Kaluwe, 2019). Also, Lusaka is also considered to be a cosmopolitan city with different cultural beliefs and myths. Thus, further investigations may reveal about the extent to which such myths influence youths into smoking marijuana. Thus, this requires investigation in that such myths may be contributing factors to smoking of marijuana among adolescents.

Also, Danseco, Kingery, and Coggshell (2019) revealed that the consequences of smoking marijuana vary from individual to individual, family to family and society to society. This shows knowledge gap in the context of where Chibolya compound in that the current prevailing factors are not established hence this research. Also, Gonzale et al., (2019) concluded in their study that some of the effects of marijuana smoking include increased levels of depressive symptoms. This also resonated with Karashiali (2022), whose study found that adolescents who used marijuana confessed that it was because of stigmatization and devaluation issues. So, marijuana was used as a defensive mechanism to escape such problems as well as for socializing and relation. This also resonates with Gonzalez et al., (2023)`s findings. Though that was the case for Karashiali`s (2022) and Gonzalez et al., (2023), it is important to find out if that is the case with Chibolya town where there are different youths are who prone to the same vices. Second, Similarly, Butler (2018) also confirmed that marijuana use is associated with anxiety and depression among adolescents as side effects. Though that was the case, research has to be undertaken to ascertain such effects through this study to find out if Butler`s (2018) findings are still prevailing in Chibolya compound to be precise.

Additionally, in their studies, Agbonghalel and Okaka (2014); Otieno (2012) and Tuwei (2014) attested that marijuana smoking is associated with lack of appetite, lack of sleep, physical weakness and rejection from friends among others. Other findings realized were poor academic performance. Unlike the aforementioned studies that were conducted in Nigeria and Kenya, this particular study will be conducted in Zambia, Lusaka to be precise to fill up the knowledge gaps

on the effects of marijuana smoking among adolescents. In other studies by Muwanzi (2019), findings were that marijuana smoking is associated with short term memory and motor skills impairment among others. Much has not been revealed in Zambia to show these effects hence this study so as to ascertain if there are such repercussions among Zambian adolescents. Another realization worthy noting is that of a study by Faeh et al.,`s (2017), which showed that marijuana smoking was mainly practiced among children in the ranges of 11 years to 15 years. Considering that there has been time frame difference between Faeh`s study and this current study, there is a likelihood of smoking weed differences of age groups. Second, the study was conducted outside Zambian and this will be undertaken in Zambia hence findings may be similar or not.

In other investigations, Yawson et al., (2022) found that that marijuana smoking was associated with suicidal thoughts and planning. The study was conducted in Nigeria, so this one will be conducted in Zambia to find out if such effects do exist in the Zambian context where the study will be conducted. Morojele et al., (2021) add that their study found that death and disability have been on the rise as consequences of juvenile smoking of marijuana among other substance abuse. This entails further investigation since there is less or no literature that make mention of such effects as far as teen smoking of marijuana is concerned.

In additionally, Zemba (2022) and Kaluwe (2019), confirmed that peer pressure, low self-esteem to mention the least lead to deviant behaviour and juvenile delinquency. This study intends to find out other factors other than those mentioned. Second, this study will be conducted in Chibolya to ascertain the kind of deviant behaviours conducted. More so, Kaluwe (2019) and Mulenga and Siziya (2021), found that bullying and excessive sexual intercourse were associated with a history of having used marijuana before. Contrary to the study site where Kaluwe (2019) and Mulenga and Siziya (2021) conducted theirs, this one will be conducted in Lusaka to find out the likelihood of any side effects or association of such vices to marijuana use among adolescents. Thus, this is a knowledge gap that has to be investigated in a different context.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter mainly focuses on the kind of research design, location of the study, the target population, sampling techniques and sample size that will be used, and the kind of data collection instruments that will be used. Still, more will be explained on the procedure for data collection, data presentation and analysis as well as ethical consideration.

3.1 Research design

According to Kombo and Tromp (2013), a research design is considered as the structure of the research. The study will adopt a descriptive research design particularly a survey design under qualitative approach because the nature of this study is in congruent with this kind of methodology. This approach is also relevant because this study endeavours to collect information about people's attitudes, opinions, habits or any of the varieties of education or social issues concerning smoking of marijuana.

3.2 Location of the study

This study will be conducted in Chibolya informal urban settlement located in the centre of Lusaka, the capital city of Zambia. The settlements is an information rich case which represents an inner city type of informal settlement, developed on undesirable land found within the city's CBD. The study area was purposively selected because it is notorious for gang violence in the city. Open air drug dealing is a common problem in this area. It is located approximately 35 kilometers from the capital, Lusaka. Chibolya sits in Chongwe Town, the district office for Chongwe District.

3.3 Target population

Population is a set of people or entities to which findings are to be generalized. Fraenkel & Wallen (1993), define target population as the group of interest to the researcher, the group to whom the researcher would like to generalize the results of the study. In the case of this study,

Chibolya compound will be the study population. However, the study target will only be youths and parents/key informants from selected households of Chibolya compound because they are victims of indiscipline and other vices.

3.4 Sampling techniques and sample size

According to Kombo & Tromp (2013), sampling technique is a sample method the researcher purposively targets a group of people believed to be reliable for the study. In the case of this study, purposive sampling technique will be used in selection of youths and some parents/key informants. The sample size will be determined by 10% of the target population according to Sultana (2017) with the help of statistics of Chibolya township population.

3.5 Data collection instrument

The possible approach for data collection will be the use of a research questionnaire and interviews. This is to allow participants to reveal what they know about the topic under study as possibly as they can. Research questionnaires and interviews are more reliable in qualitative approach of research and especially when they are structured with open and closed ended questions on the topic. This in itself is advantageous to participants in expressing their views on the matter.

3.6 Data collection procedures

The possible procedure for data collection will be guided by obtaining permits from relevant government offices and the researcher's institution. Then possible convenient arrangements will be made on when to administer questionnaires to participants and collect them later once filled with data for further data proceedings. Interviews will also be arranged after consents will be obtained from the responses.

3.7 Data presentation and analysis

Data analysis is the process of reducing large amounts of collected data to make sense of them. It involves uncovering underlying structures; extracting important variables detecting any anomalies and testing any underlying assumptions. After collecting data, the researcher will process it as a way of correcting or identifying problems in the raw data if there will be any before doing any analysis. Then data will be presented into possible tables, charts and bar graphs where necessary

with the help of Microsoft excel. Microsoft excel is very useful in the analysis of social science research of this kind. Thematic Analysis (TA) will also be used where necessary. This will involve data familiarisation’, ‘coding generation’, ‘looking for themes’, ‘reviewing and refining themes’ and ‘theme labelling’ and so forth. further proceedings will be about interpretations and discussion of the findings.

3.8 Ethical consideration

Ethics refers to moral principles suggested by an individual or group that is widely accepted and which offer rules and behavioural expectations towards respondents and other stakeholders in research (Baron, 2006). Indeed, rights and protection of the privacy of participants will be highly considered while conducting research, especially upon collecting data. As already clearly stated, permits and consents will be considered before venturing into the actual data collection to avoid violating any rules or privacy of individuals. This is to say respondents will participate at their own free will unlike being compelled to participate. More importantly, respondents will be assured that whatever information that will be provided will be treated confidential as it will not be shared or used for anything else except for the purpose of this particular study.

REFERENCES

A Canadian Addiction Survey, (2018). *‘Long term heavy cannabis use: implications for health education’*, Drugs: Education, Prevention and Policy, Vol. 11, No. 4, pp. 299–313

- ACMD, K. (2003). *Hidden Harm: Responding to the Needs of the Children of Problem Drug Users*. London: Home Office.
- Agbonghalel, K. and Okaka, L. (2014), *Relation between substance use and depression among Spanish adolescents*. International journal of Psychology and Psychological Therapy, 11, 79- 90.
- Bandura, A. (1977), *Social Learning Theory*, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Baron, I. (2006). *Effects of cannabis use on human behavior, including cognition, motivation, and psychosis: A review*. JAMA Psychiatry 2016;73:292–297
- Barret, J. (1986), “*Drug Abuse: Prevention Strategies for schools,*” in ERIC Digest 17.
- Bourassa, O. and Vaugoeis, L. (2015). *The Praeger International Collection on Addictions: Faces of addiction, then and now*. Manchester – UK: ABC- CC10.
- Bourne, H. (2015) ‘*Parental and peer influences on the risk of adolescent drug use*’, *The Journal of Primary Prevention*, Vol. 26, No. 6, pp. 529–51
- Butler, O. (2018). *Alcoholism and the Family*: New York, Franklin Watts.
- Connell, P. (2014). *Effects of Alcoholism, Chilling Discoveries*. Kenya Education Guide.
- Curran, E. (2016) “*Drug Prevention Education in School: The Malaysian Experience*” In *Drug Prevention Policy*, Vol. 6, No. 3.
- Curran, K. (2016) *Becoming a Marijuana User*. American Journal Of Sociology. 59(3): 235- 242.

- Danseco, K. and Cogghel, P. (2019) *An Investigation Of The Factors Contributing To Drug And Substance Abuse Among The Youth In Kenya: A Survey Of Select Rehabilitation Centres In Mombasa County*. International Journal of Public Health, 1(5), 53-70.
- DEC, (2021) “*Rapid Assessment of Drug abuse in Kenya: A National Report.*”
- Dembo, P. (1994). *Illicit drug use and treatment in South Africa: A review*. Substance Use & Misuse.
- Di Forti, J. (2019). ‘*Understanding reasons for drug use amongst young people: a functional perspective*’, Health Education Research, Vol. 16, No. 4, pp. 457–69
- Ekpenyong, G. (2012). *Approaches to substance use prevention utilizing school curriculum plus social environment change: Addictive behaviours*.
- Ekpenyong, R. (2012). *Adolescent illegal drug use: the impact of personality, family and environmental factors*’, Journal of Behavioural Medicine, Vol. 24, No. 2, pp. 183–203
- EMCDDA, G. (2015) “*Preventing Adolescent Drug abuse through a Multimodal Cognitive-behaviour Approach: Results of a 3-year study*”. Journal of Consult Clinical Psychology 58(4), 437 – 446.
- Faeh, N. (2017). *Youth substance abuse; Gaps in services, research and policy*. In Substance Abuse in Canada; Youth in Focus. Canadian Centre on Substance Abuse.
- Fraenkel, P & Wallen, R. (1993) *Cannabis, identity and the male teenage friendship group [dissertation]*. Manchester (UK): Manchester Metropolitan University

- Gerrard, P (1999) *Global Health Risks: Mortality and burden of disease attributable to selected major risks*.
- Gonzalez, K. (2019), *Report on Customary Criminal Offences in Kenya. California – USA: The Government Printer*.
- González, K. (2023). *Report on Customary Criminal Offences in Kenya. California – USA: The Government Printer*.
- Green, T.R. (2003) *Preventing Drug Abuse through the schools: Intervention programme That Work in NIDA Conference on Drugs*, (<http://www.drugabuse.gov/drugpage.html>)
- Hathaway, J. (2011) “*The Effect of School-based Substance Abuse Education: A Meta-analysis*”. *Journal of drug Education*, 18(3), 243-264.
- Hathaway, L. (2011). *Cannabis and tobacco use: where are the boundaries? A qualitative study on cannabis consumption modes among adolescents*. *Health education research*, 25(1), 74–82. <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cyp027>
- Ike (2009) “*Essentials of Business Research: A Guide to Doing Your Research Project*” SAGE Publications.
- Johnston, K. (2011). “*Drug Education: A review of British Government Policy and Evidence of Effectiveness*”, *Health Education Research Theory and Practice* 14 (4), 491 -505.
Retrieved 03 / 05 / 2011
- Kaluwe, N. (2019), *An assessment of the effects of drug abuse on pupils’ academic performance. A Case Study Of One Of The Primary Schools. Cavendish University Zambia (Cuz)*.

- Karashiali, O. (2022). *Deviant Behavior and Self Enhancement in Adolescent*. Journal of Youth Adolescent 7: 253 – 277.
- Khan, I and Arnott, Y. (2018), *Drug abuse among the youth in Kenya*. International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research, 2(6).
- Kombo, R. and Tromp, Y. (2013) *Identity, youth and crisis*. New York: W. W. Norton Company.
- Lakhampal, K and Agnihotri, L. (2017) '*Cannabis, motivation and life satisfaction in an internet sample*', *Substance Abuse Treatment, Prevention and Policy*, Vol. 1, No. 2 (12 January), accessed at www.substanceabusepolicy.com
- Mafumbate, H. (2016). *Prevalence and correlates of marijuana use in Canada*. Heal Reports. 2016;26(4):10–5.
- Masenga, L. (2017) *The Nature and Effects of Substance Abuse among Adolescents*: The Lancet Psychiatry, 6(5), 427-436. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366\(19\)30048-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366(19)30048-3)
- Masiye, Ndhlovu K. & Kasonde-Ng'andu, M. (2019). *Education and prevention needs to take account of positive personal and social functions that different substances serve young people*', *Addiction*, Vol. 94, No. 7, pp. 1043–50
- Morojele et al, (2021) *Drug-taking among Nigerian students at universities in the United States of America*. Bulletin of Narcotics, 39(2); 75-80.
- Mugenda, O.M and Mugenda, A.G. (2003): *Research methods; Quantitative and qualitative approaches*. Nairobi. Acts press.

- Ndhlovu, M. (2019). *Relationships as determinants of substance use amongst street children in a local government area in south-western Nigeria*. South African Family Practice, 50, 47-47d.
- NHS Digital, (2018). *Literature Review one Drug Education in schools: Curriculum and teaching*, Queensland: NP. Retrieved 01/08/10
- NHS Digital, M. (2018) *An improved brief measure of cannabis misuse: the Cannabis Use Disorders Identification Test-Revised (CUDIT-R)*. Drug and alcohol dependence, 110(1-2), 137–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2010.02.017>
- Nkonge, M. (2015) *Illicit Drug use by Secondary School Learners in Windhoek, Namibia*. Master Thesis, University of South Africa
- Otieno,G. (2012). *Adolescent problem behaviour; The influence of parents and peers*. Behaviour Research and Therapy, 37; 217-30.
- Pudney, K. (2018). *Further Considerations of the Classification of Cannabis under the Misuse of Drugs Act 1971*. London: Home Office.
- Sultana, Y.S (2017) *Fundamentals of Social Research Methods; An African Perspective*. Lusaka; Government Printers.
- Tuwei K. (2014) *Drug abuse among street children*. Journal of Clinical Research in HIV AIDS and Prevention, 3(3), 12-45. DOI; 10.14302/issn.2324-7339.jcrhap-18-2291
- WHO, (2012). *World drug report 2012: drug use and health Consequnces*. United Nations publications,.

WHO, (2022) *World drug report 2022: drug use and health Consequnces*. United Nations publications,.

WHO. (2016). *The health and social effects of nonmedical cannabis use*. Available: http://www.who.int/substance_abuse/publications/cannabis_report/en

WHO. (2018). *Global school-based student health survey (GSHS) purpose and methodology*. Available: <http://www.who.int/ncds/surveillance/gshs/methodology/en>

World Youth Report (2003)

Yawson, W. (2022). *Factors influencing drug and substance abuse among the youth in Kenya. A Case Study Of Likii Sublocation, Laikipia East Sub-County*.

Zemba N. (2022), *The Marihuana Problem: An Overview*. Am J Psychiatry 1968;125:370–8. doi:10.1176/ajp.125.3.370.